

Log Periodic Folded Slot Array Antenna for an Autonomous Cryobot Synthetic Aperture Radar for Subsurface Exploration of Europa

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Abstract—In this paper a log periodic folded slot antenna array is described for a forward-looking synthetic aperture radar (IceSAR) system for the ‘Very deep Autonomous Laser-powered Kilowatt-class Yo-yoing Robotic Ice explorer’ (VALKYRIE) cryobot project. Design and performance characterization of the log periodic antennas is presented along with a first light radar imagery obtained during in situ operation to prove the feasibility of this design for use in a cryobot obstacle avoidance and mapping system.

Index Terms— conformal log periodic folded slot array antenna, forward-looking SAR

I. INTRODUCTION

Analysis of the European subsurface from past missions indicate the presence of a saline ocean under the ice cover thus making Europa a prime-candidate in the search for extraterrestrial life [1],[2]. The SAR system described in this paper will provide critical forward-looking obstacle avoidance capabilities to the VALKYRIE ice-penetrating cryobot vehicle. Technologies demonstrated in the VALKYRIE project will enable future lander missions to the ice-covered moon of Jupiter, Europa [3].

II. PROTOTYPE DESIGN

The development of a synthetic aperture radar system consists of two parts. First is the design of an array of four conformal log-periodic folded slot array (LPFSA) antennas that provide a main lobe in the forward direction while operating within the ultra-high frequency (UHF) band. Second part involves the design of the radar analog and digital system SAR data processing. This paper focuses on the design and characterization of the antenna array and feasibility of using it in a forward looking SAR system.

A. Antenna design

The type of antenna identified for the IceSAR system is a conformal Log Periodic Folded Slot Array (LPFSA) [4], which makes use of an antenna structure complementary to the conventional log periodic dipole array antenna [5]. A LPFSA antenna has a radially polarized electric field vector, wide impedance bandwidth (0.7 to 1 GHz) and conformability to curved surfaces. The antennas radiate in

the presence of a ~ 1.5 cm thick layer of water annulus created by the melting of the cryobot through ice. An array of four such antennas will be used so as to allow resolution of left-right ambiguity in the radar image.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: Fabricated (a) resonant cavities and (b) CPW antenna panel.

The IceSAR antenna is designed with resonant metallic cavity backing to make use of the envelope of melted glacial water (~ 1.5 cm thick layer with real relative permittivity, $\epsilon_r = 81$ and conductivity, $\sigma \sim 3.5 \mu S/cm$) as a high permittivity dielectric. This allows for quarter wavelength resonant cavities even when geometrical constraints preclude quarter wavelength depth as in the case of air filled cavities. Fabricated resonant cavities are shown in Figure 1(a). One of the fabricated antenna panels is also shown, in Figure 1(b).

III. ANTENNA CHARACTERIZATION

Outdoor laboratory tests for antenna characterization were carried out at an outdoor laboratory in Austin, Texas. In situ testing of the antennas and operation of the IceSAR system was carried out on the Matanuska Glacier in Alaska.

A. Laboratory antenna characterization

Initial testing of the antenna array attached to the cryobot melt head was carried out in a 30 inches diameter by 70 inches tall (\sim one ton) cylindrical block of ice at the outdoor laboratory in Austin, TX (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Antennas melting inside an ice cylinder at the outdoor laboratory in Austin, Texas.

Reflection coefficient measurements and front lobe radiation characterization of the LPFSA antennas using a previously characterized reference log-periodic dipole array antenna (LPDA) are shown in Figure 3 along with the comparisons to simulations using Ansoft HFSS. The HFSS model used for simulating the structure was designed with a 1.5-cm cylindrical fresh water layer around the antenna. The LPDA probe was translated under the antenna being tested to measure front lobe radiation. Measurements were recorded at 25 cm linear intervals.

Figure 3: Measured (a) reflection coefficient and (b) front lobe radiation.

B. In situ tests on Matanuska Glacier, Alaska

In situ testing of the LPFSA antennas and IceSAR radar system was carried out on the Matanuska Glacier, Alaska. Ice boring was achieved using a hot water heater/pump

(“Hotsy”) along with the same melt head attached to the antenna as was used at Stone Aerospace.

Figure 4 shows, in terms of normalized power, the reconstructed image formed by coherent aggregation of pre-detected reflected signals received in the synthetic aperture formed by the melting of the cryobot [6]. The transmit and receive antenna are the same for this image. It is important to note however that the left-right ambiguity inherent to forward looking SAR systems is not resolved in the reconstructed image.

Figure 4: First-light radar backscatter image reconstructed from coherent integration of 604 radar echoes.

SUMMARY

Design, testing and in situ characterization and operation of the radar system including reconstruction of a first-light image has been presented in this paper. Resolution of the left-right ambiguity in radar image reconstruction using the set of four LPFSA antenna array is currently on going.

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